

Name _____
 Date _____
 Workshop _____
 Location _____

Entrepreneurial skills
 for young social innovators
 in an open digital world

Please read each question carefully and indicate what applies to you.

	Question	not at all --	rather no -	undecided 0	rather yes +	yes totally ++
1	Are you afraid of doing things you have never done before?	0	0	0	0	0
2	Are you as clever as other children?	0	0	0	0	0
3	Can you do most things without the help of others?	0	0	0	0	0
4	Do you know which things you can do well?	0	0	0	0	0
5	Can you do a task even if it is hard?	0	0	0	0	0
6	Can you do as much as other children?	0	0	0	0	0
7	Do other children know more than you?	0	0	0	0	0
8	Can you do most things as long as you do not give up?	0	0	0	0	0
9	Are you afraid of doing tricky things?	0	0	0	0	0
10	Do you often succeed better than others?	0	0	0	0	0
11	Can you figure out new things even if they are very tricky?	0	0	0	0	0
12	Do you prefer trying new things to things you are used to?	0	0	0	0	0
13	Can you learn new things that are shown to you?	0	0	0	0	0
14	Do other children often have better ideas than you?	0	0	0	0	0
15	Do you prefer not to learn many new things?	0	0	0	0	0
16	Do you want to become your own boss?	0	0	0	0	0

THANK YOU!!!